

QUIZ

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PROGRAM CODE: DILT

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: Quiz

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied XUS conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author x did use Zotero to insert references

The author x did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **The author-date style formatting is commonly used within the social and natural and physical sciences. In its most common application, this format...**
 - Is a way to write so that you can impress your readers who have not researched your topic well enough.
 - Uses parenthetical citation next to the reference, including the author, date, and relevant page numbers therefore emphasizing the author-date style in capturing citations.¹**
 - Uses no parenthetical citations next to the reference but includes these at the bottom of the page as footnotes with the author, date, and relevant page numbers therefore emphasizing the author-date style citations.
 - Is a way to reference block quotes and to offer author date information that can be easily referenced as one reads through the essay.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 128.

2. **The objective of doing a dissertation is to...**
- Obtain the appropriate discipline credentials by demonstrating that you understand and can, therefore, conduct good research.²**
 - Obtain the credentials that help you to teach in the area of study and therefore be recognized as an expert.
 - Get a degree that can help you get a better job.
 - Get the highest regard among your peers as a learned person.
3. **The following are examples of Plagiarism. Which one is not?**
- Taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author.
 - Consulting multiple sources, carefully gleaning valuable information from these sources, and then writing your own response with appropriate citations where necessary.³**
 - Using a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.
 - Having someone draft a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 6.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 5.

4. **A key suggestion to good academic writing is to take the views you are discussing seriously. This means among other things that...**
- You need to practice the concept of "arguing against yourself" to be sure whatever you are communicating can withstand subject area experts' criticisms.⁴**
 - Always assume your arguments are wrong and therefore offer them with tons of qualifications and caveats.
 - Treat all the writers and philosophers of the topics in your subject as if they knew all the information and therefore just learn and pass that along.
 - Do not worry or incorporate any responses and criticisms for your writings because as a researcher, you clearly are dealing with the current information, which others may not be aware of.
5. **Research is an intentional process of study that includes the pursuit of understanding of a specific topic. Which of the following statement best describes how researchers think about the aims of their study?**
- A researcher is only interested in any data on a topic and should not be too worried about questions like why.
 - A Researcher looks for specific data that they can use as evidence to test and support an answer to a question that their topic inspired them to ask, including why.⁵**
 - A research can always use data to tell a story even when they do not have enough sources to support their assertions.
 - A research lets data lead them wherever it will and does not question it as long as they have enough material to write their thesis.

⁴ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 15.

⁵ Turabian, 15.

6. **When planning an argument to be laid out in writing for a research study, a researcher needs to...**

- Imagine a discussion with the readers and develop your argumentation as a process for an invitation to solve a problem and whose solution the readers may not fully accept.⁶**
- Include all your notes from research and try to convince the readers that your newfound knowledge trumps all former written monographs.
- Be overly cautious in your argumentation offering caveats to your argument and always leaving room for the opposition and further studies.
- Use as many big terms as possible and information to make sure you sound learned and an authority in the field.

7. **Citing sources using the notes-bibliography style is...**

- The process of including the bibliographical information as part of your text so that there is no difference between the quote and your own writing.
- Placing references at the end of the document and not supplying any superscript or other endnote formatting.
- The process of placing a subscript number to show a source with footnotes at the bottom of the page and a list of sources provided at the end of the paper.⁷**
- The process of supplying the bibliographical sources using block quotes and associated notes.

⁶ Turabian, 36.

⁷ Turabian, 90.

8. **Zotero is a bibliographical organizing tool that should be used,**
- As a way to reduce the number of times one has to refer to sources when researching and writing.
 - As a tool for making the essay look sophisticated and convincing to the readers.
 - As a tool to support the research process and to appropriately store and reference all sources one uses in an essay.⁸**
 - A tool you must use because Euclid University requires it in the writing process.
9. **There are several ways to represent other writers including direct quotes. Quotations are...**
- One way of proving to your readers that you accessed lots of materials and are therefore every smart.
 - One way of accurately denoting sources used which helps in avoiding plagiarism but also giving due credit to the author or the source.⁹**
 - Extremely confusing and should be omitted all together to allow the reader work through the easy easily.
 - Must always be placed at the beginning of any argument that you are supporting and referred to and shown by a superscript numeral in the text.

⁸ Euclid University, "ACA-401 Period 3," Course site, Euclid LMS, accessed January 12, 2021, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-3/>.

⁹ Turabian, 208.

10. **Many researchers are good at writing and can develop a first draft that is convincing and ready for publication with relative ease. Why is this statement wrong?**
- Because organizing an essay using basic writing formats including having a thesis, body, arguments, and a conclusion is not that difficult.
 - Because some people are naturally smart and can write eloquently without needing to revise their material.
 - Because to qualify for graduate level research, one needs to have mastered the process of proficient writing.
 - Because writing is about meeting the needs and expectations of their readers, and this is rarely achieved through a first draft. Revising and re-writing is part of the process of developing a convincing argument.¹⁰**

¹⁰ Turabian, 68.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Euclid University. "ACA-401 Period 3." Course site. Euclid LMS. Accessed January 12, 2021. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-3/>.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.